

RADIANT CREATOR WORKSHOP Traditional Tomato

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Hosted by: Institute of Agrostrategies and Innovations (IAI)

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background and objectives

RADIANT (ReAlising DynamIc vAlue chaiNs for underuTilised crops) proposes a set of strategic and fully inclusive multi-actor driven solutions, supported by practical tools and multi-actor engagement methods, to realize Dynamic Value Chains (DVCs) for underutilised crops (UCs).

Acknowledging integration of agrobiodiversity into value chains is a long-term challenge, and to accelerate change, RADIANT selected a core collection of 15 well-developed and adapted UCs whose benefits make them worthy and timely for wider inclusion in biodiverse value chains. Conditions under which a crop is regarded neglected or underutilised vary greatly, and this alone calls for specific analyses and interventions. These core crops, along with an extended collection of UCs, are keystones of 20 Pilot- or AURORA-Farms. The AURORA Farms will serve as knowledge and inspiration-hubs for co-creation of new, alternative, and more-sustainable management options – showcasing opportunities for integration of UCs in value chains and bringing locally-grown diversity from farmers to consumers, celebrating national and regional heritage, developing local good-food culture, and realise more-sustainable business opportunities.

The aim of this workshop was to showcase traditional crop varieties from the Plovdiv region in Bulgaria, focusing on how traditional tomato crops can be brought to farmers' fields and consumers' tables – what are the possibilities and challenges posed by this endeavour – as an adaptive response to the climatic and socioeconomic crisis that Mediterranean agriculture is facing. The diverse range of stakeholders

related to these crops discussed the opportunities and obstacles in the adoption of traditional horticultural crops on the part of producers and consumers.

1.2 Workshop framework and participants

The programme of the event included a series of lectures/presentations by different stakeholders. These included the Project Coordinator (Marta Vasconcelos), Bulgarian partnership coordinator (Svetlana Boyanova), and representatives from the Bulgarian AURORA farm (Hristo Tsvetanov), Agricultural University of Plovdiv (Bojin Bojinov), MVCRI (Gancho Pasev), Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (Vasil Georgiev) and the CEO of the Bulgarian Association for Modern Trade (Nikolay Valkanov). Showcasing the viewpoints of producers, academics, breeders, and grocery chains on the current state and the perspectives for the broader adoption of UCs set the stage for fruitful discussions. A tasting exercise for consumers was also organised during Day 1, which was combined with a survey of farmers' and consumers' perception of local tomato varieties as UC. On Day 2, another tasting session was organized with producers to introduce a specific underutilised variety of tomato and take part in discussions before and after tasting (through a 2-step survey) on their perception of what would help to expand the use of this UC (see the programme of the workshop in Annex I).

The following stakeholder participation distribution was recorded (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of the participants by stakeholder groups.

2. Presentations

2.1 Presentations Overview

A series of presentations given at the beginning of the event are summarised below. Presentations can also be found [here](#).

Introduction to RADIANT project from the Project Leader

Marta Vasconcelos

The RADIANT project stands for realizing dynamic value chains for underutilised crops. It's a project that has 29 partners, from 12 countries, having the same goals – to promote and valorize the underutilised crops for food, feed, and nonfood. In RADIANT, we work with different types of underutilised crops such as legumes, cereals, horticultural crops, etc. RADIANT includes a large, multidisciplinary

team. Each team has their specific expertise in the field of agroecology and biodiversity, farming and agronomy, breeding and genomics, socio – economics and consumers studies, nutrition and health, value chain analyses, enabling technologies, marketing, dissemination, and exploitation. RADIANT is divided into work packages, which have essential core, we call Aurora farms. In RADIANT we also have a dedicated work in the field of plant breeding to make underutilised crops more competitive. Finally, the project promotes biodiversity in agronomy to improve the utilisation of possible resources.

Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovations as a partner to RADIANT and other EU-funded projects

Svetlana Boyanova

The Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovations is a key player in national agro-food policy development and a participant in several EU projects and initiatives such as: AgroDigiRise, Digital Europe Programme, DLTechUp, and

RADIANT project. The European Institute for Innovation and Technology in Food (EIT Food) commissioned the Institute for Agricultural Strategies and Innovations (IAI) to fulfill the role of EIT Food Hub for Bulgaria in 2020. Within the RADIANT project, tomato was chosen as the underutilised crop of choice. The work in progress includes:

- initial policy analysis on the legislative status of UC crops;
- screening of a collection of local varieties for their agronomical

and antioxidant properties;

- metabolite profiling of both the initial collection and the F₁ plants from the two crosses;
- genetic analysis of the diversity of the collection and the homogeneity of F₁; and,
- cultivation, genotyping and phenotyping of the F₂ and F₃ generations so that prospective breeding materials can be proposed for development into varieties with improved antioxidant content, taste and yield.

In collaboration with other RADIANT partners, further policy recommendations are to be developed prior to dissemination at national and EU levels.

Research activities of AUP team in the context of food quality improvement

Bojin Bojinov

The research activities in Bulgaria within the RADIANT project are focused on three main crops: pepper, tomatoes, and bean. Hot pepper studies so far focused on genes Pun 1 (4 alleles), CaMYB31 (partially sequenced), pAMT, metabolomic and genomics in general. Whilst in terms of bean, a traditional but underutilised crop in Bulgaria, there are established scientific-based breeding programmes to ensure protein security in the country. Within the RADIANT project:

- 1) a tomato collection was planted and phenotyped;

- 2) genetic homogeneity of hybrid progenies was studied for F₁ hybrid nature checking;
- 3) genetic diversity within accession was conducted;
- 4) combined genotypic data was analyzed; and,
- 5) metabolic profiling was carried out.

All the data were combined to build a new generation breeding programme with a focus to bring to the producers and consumers competitive varieties of underutilised crops such tomato.

MVCRI as a key maintainer and breeding institution for underutilised vegetable crops in Bulgaria

Gancho Pasev

MVCRI was created in 1930 and has:

- 180 ha arable land;
- 1,75 ha glass/steel greenhouses; and,
- 0,35 ha polyethylene greenhouses.

The main research groups are the ones on Horticultural breeding and Crop production. They participate in multiple National and EU-funded projects, while also attracting funding from the IAEA (International Atomic Energy Agency). Crop breeding activities cover tomato, pepper, potato, cabbages, eggplant, onion, pumpkin, garden peas and Zucchini. In tomato, more than 20 varieties and hybrids were developed in the last 20 years, with many of them well accepted by the local producers and consumers.

The role of medium-sized and large commercial retail entities in promoting local crops

Nikolay Valkanov

Analysis of the current situation of the Bulgarian fruits and vegetables market was presented with the share of the retail chains, open-air markets, online trade, etc., discussed in the context of short- and long-term trends. Particular

attention was given to the various initiatives of the big retailers for promoting locally produced fresh vegetables and the effect they have on consumers' education and purchasing habits.

Efficient metabolic profiling for fruit quality improvement

Vasil Georgiev

Upon a brief introduction to the origins of tomato crop and the accumulation of health-beneficial compounds in the fruit, the work of the Department of Analytical Chemistry and Physical Chemistry, Technological Faculty, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv,

Bulgaria was presented, which focused on developing methodologies for efficient metabolic profiling for tomato fruit quality. Beneficial properties of the various groups of antioxidants present in tomato fruits were discussed in the context of their relative availability. Both specific and overall antioxidant activities in various local accessions and breeding lines were presented and the potential for developing improved new breeding materials discussed.

Chemapool as RADIANT AURORA Farm

Hristo Tzvetanov

The main activities in the farm were presented:

- 1) field crops production (~3 000 ha);
- 2) activity in growing fruits (cherries and plums) and vegetables – tomato (incl. landraces), sweet pepper, cabbages, etc.; and,
- 3) horticultural activities on about 13 ha, 0.6 ha highly intensive greenhouse, 1.5 ha plastic greenhouses, 8 ha open vegetable growing, 2 ha orchard.

The main aim of Chemapool involvement in RADIANT is to popularize fruit and vegetable landraces and local breeds. Key points in achieving it are:

- know your target market (size and attractive price points);
- follow changes in consumer preferences;

- follow/participate in legislative modifications; and,
- proactively develop new market niches.

3. Demonstration activity / Field visit

3.1. Tasting exercise with consumers and other stakeholders

During the first day of the event, a tasting exercise was organised with consumers. First, they were introduced to the various properties of different local varieties and breeding materials. This was followed by the actual tasting of some products. A survey was then conducted with the consumers to collect information on their perception of the local UCs after learning about various aspects of the UC's benefits, production, and distribution challenges.

3.2. Tasting exercise with farmers

During the second day of the event, a tasting exercise with a survey was organised with producers. The survey was split into two parts. First, participants were asked to answer questions based on what they already knew and what they learned from the presentations and discussions in Day 1. This was followed by the actual tasting of some products and an *ad-hoc* SWOT analysis of the production – distribution – sales chain. The second part of the survey was aimed at collecting information on the farmers' perception of the local UCs after getting more knowledge on various aspects of UC's benefits, production and distribution challenges during the SWOT analysis.

The surveys for the farmers and consumers were conducted under the guidance of Simone Piras, at the Social, Economic & Geographical Sciences Department of the James Hutton Institute (UK.)

3.3. Visit to the R&D facilities of the MVCRI

On Day 2 of the event, a visit to the R&D facilities of the hosting institution (MVCRI) was organised for all participants – farmers, consumers, academics, breeders, retailers. The visit was aimed at

familiarizing stakeholders with the basic and applied knowledge that is underlying (and indeed incorporated) in the maintenance of local diversity and the development of new locally-adapted varieties of UCs. It included visits to the laboratories for evaluating physical and biochemical properties of horticultural crops, as well as laboratories for the identification and detection of pests and diseases. Visitors were split into two groups so that they can better appreciate the diversity and sophistication of the equipment involved as well as the actual requirements and the proper set-ups for properly evaluating various fruit qualities – taste, aroma, color, firmness, sweetness/acidity, etc.

4. Outputs of discussions

Within the CREATOR workshop, we implemented separate discussions for farmers and consumers. The results are summarised in this section.

4.1 Farmers discussion

The meeting with farmers started with the completion of a survey including a discrete choice experiment (DCE), followed by a discussion about the potential for creating a dynamic value chain of the IDEAL tomato variety also involving a SWOT analysis. At the end of the session, participants were asked to complete again the DCE aimed to assessing the impact, if any, of the discussion. Overall, nine farmers participated. Their data were later integrated with 12 responses received online. The latter are not included in the data analysis below since they did not participate in the subsequent discussion.

Participating farmers were relatively young, with 4 of them aged under 35, and the oldest 2 aged 55 to 64; 7 were female; and 7 had achieved a university degree, of which 4 was in agriculture. For 7 of them, farming was the main source of household income, which in turn was in the upper half of the suggested distribution (over €817 per month) for all but one participant. The farm size was very skewed: 5 respondents were using less than 10 hectares, one 180, and one 300, for an average of 94 hectares. The number of years working in farming was also very varied, ranging from less than 1 year to 30 years, with an average of 12. However, the period managing their own farm was much shorter, 4.8 years on average. Seven farmers specialised in horticultural crops, of which 2 jointly with cereals and potatoes

respectively; 1 specialised on potatoes, and 1 did not indicate a specialisation.

All the participants knew the IDEAL variety of tomato before attending the workshop, and 8 had previously grown it, of which 6 in the last 5 years. It was grown on less than 10% of the land area, which corresponded to around 1 hectare for two of them, 15 for one, and 18 for another one. However, when confronted with the possibility of growing underutilised crops (UCs) in general (assessed by means of a five-point Likert scale), they showed a risk averse-attitude, with most agreeing that **changing well-established farming practices is difficult and that administrative as well as technical assistance is required**. Moreover, they express **the need to see a price premium, accessible seeds, and safe returns**. The most agreed upon statements were that **there are limited market opportunities to adopt novel crops**, and that they would **only adopt these crops if they were suitable for local climatic conditions and resistant to pests**. In turn, they seemed less worried about their own ability to manage novel crops, and about what other farmers do. In terms of risks, uncertainty in selling prices was the main one, followed by pests and diseases that can reduce yield. Market access was also mentioned as an important barrier.

The farmers completed a DCE aimed at identifying the factors influencing their crop choices. They were asked to choose between farming plans representing different characteristics, with the possibility of opting out. Each of the 9 farmers made 9 choices, resulting in a total of 81 observations. The results of the data analysis are illustrated in Table 1. First, it is interesting to note that only a limited number of significant factors were reported. Focusing on the first choice, farmers

preferred to devote a smaller percentage of their land to the plan and had a negative preference for varieties producing a low fruit yield. They also had a strong preference for varieties presenting multi-stress tolerance (they would accept lower selling prices in exchange for it) and, as expected, for higher selling prices.

Table 1. Multinomial logistic (MNL) models for farmers' choices on adoption of the farming plans (before and after discussion).

Characteristics of the farming plan	First choice		Second choice	
	Coefficient	WTA	Coefficient	WTA
Accepting a plan (vs Not accepting)	-0.472	0.972	1.457	-7.316
Percentage of land devoted to the farming plan	-0.016**	0.032**	-0.009	0.045
Variety: IDEAL (vs Commercial)	-0.436	0.899	-0.839	4.212
Variety: Hybrid (vs Commercial)	-0.315	0.650	-0.382	1.918
Fruit yield per plant: Low (vs Medium)	-0.799*	1.646	-0.743*	3.732
Fruit yield per plant: High (vs Medium)	0.215	-0.444	-0.177	0.890
Multi-stress tolerance (vs No tolerance)	1.627***	-	1.361***	-
Perishability of the product: Low (vs Medium)	0.317	3.352***	0.144	6.836**
Perishability of the product: High (vs Medium)	0.182	-0.653	0.156	-0.721
Access to free technical assistance (vs No access)	-0.035	-0.375	0.284	-0.783
Selling price per ton (1,000 BGN)	-0.035	0.073	0.284	-1.429
	0.485***	n.a.	0.199**	n.a.

Notes: Baseline attribute levels in parentheses. WTA = willingness-to-accept, in 1,000 BGN. Significance levels: * 0.10, ** 0.05, *** 0.01.

After the DCE, the discussion centred around a SWOT analysis focused on the goal of developing a dynamic value chain for the IDEAL variety in Bulgaria. Farmers indicated multiple elements for each category (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats). We acknowledge the potential for subjective interpretations, as what one person sees as

a strength might be viewed as a weakness by someone else. Key findings in this regard are:

- **Strengths:** Overall, four farmers highlighted taste as the most important strength of the IDEAL variety, followed by the good yield (two farmers), as well as resistance to pests and diseases and good adaptation to local climatic conditions (one farmer each).
- **Weaknesses:** Low resistance to diseases was highlighted as the main weakness by four farmers, followed by low yield (two farmers), and not being an improved hybrid variety (one).
- **Opportunities:** The potential for genetic improvement was considered as a key opportunity by two farmers, followed by taste as a tool for marketability (two farmers). Positive perception by consumers on the market and adaptability were also mentioned (one farmer each), while a possible improvement to its disease resistance was thought to be another putative opportunity.
- **Threats:** The potential outbreak of new diseases (three farmers) and the low yield (two) were seen as the main threats to its broader adoption. Market factors, including price, limited transportability and “difficult market” in general were perceived as additional threats, in addition to climatic changes (one farmer each).

During the discussion, several farmers provided valuable additional insights. One farmer mentioned the cultural significance and traditional value of the IDEAL variety, but highlighted the difficulties in finding seeds, which points to the **need for wider seed availability**. On a more positive note, a farmer reported their success in growing the IDEAL variety in their garden, even without fertiliser, pointing to **its potential for sustainable growth methods**.

However, some concerns were also raised regarding market availability and seasonality, with questions about how many months per year the IDEAL variety is accessible. The main issue seems to be a lack of labelling, resulting in consumers either not necessarily knowing they are consuming the IDEAL variety and hence recognize its unique taste or are consuming other varieties believing they are IDEAL. **Proper labelling could increase awareness and demand.** Another challenge is the seed misuse, whereby some farmers misuse subsidised seeds by claiming subsidies and planting other varieties. Additionally, the impact of weather was mentioned as a concern, as it can cause cracking of the IDEAL tomatoes, making them less suitable for sale. This suggests that **there is a need to develop more resilient varieties and educate farmers about optimal growing conditions.** Finally, some farmers expressed uncertainty about proper watering and fertilising practices, which suggests a need for comprehensive technical support.

After the discussion, farmers were asked to retake the same choice experiment between pairs of farming plans. The results are shown in the last two columns of Table 1. Overall, 22% of their choice changed following the discussion. However, the characteristics of the plans chosen do not differ significantly apart from the price, which becomes lower ($p = 0.028$ in a t -test). The second choices see a higher prevalence of the commercial variety rather than IDEAL or a hybrid, but the difference is not significant. Overall, the dynamics observed before the discussion remain valid although less pronounced: farmers do not like low fruit yield but are attracted by multi-stress tolerance and by higher selling prices.

In conclusion, while several current challenges were mentioned, the discussion also revealed good opportunities for the IDEAL variety. Hence, by addressing issues such as improved labelling, stricter seed distribution, research into resistant varieties, and providing clear guidelines and resources, the IDEAL variety has the potential to thrive in the marketplace for both farmers and consumers.

4.2 Consumers discussion

The consumers workshop entailed the completion of a DCE questionnaire, followed by a short discussion on the potential of the IDEAL variety. Overall, 11 participants took part in the workshop, followed by the collection of 11 additional responses online. Since the questionnaire was exactly the same and the discussion was not meant to constitute a treatment (differently from farmers), responses are discussed jointly.

The sample was relatively young, with 64% of the respondents aged under 35, and others ranging different age groups, the oldest being 55 to 64 years old. Half of them were female. The level of education was high, with all but 2 (91%) having undergraduate or postgraduate education. In terms of income, the largest group (36%) fell into the highest category (over €1,840), but they were distributed along the full scale, with 36% located in the middle of the range. Noteworthy, 64% stated that, sometimes, their households face economic difficulties. It is also worth mentioning that food shopping and cooking were done mostly or exclusively by someone else in the household for 68% of the respondents. Nevertheless, 68% declared that their diet is 'somewhat' healthy and 'somewhat' diverse, the remaining ones that it is 'very' healthy and diverse; only 1 stated that their diet is not diverse.

Overall, 50% of the participants shopped primarily from supermarkets, 23% from local independent shops, 14% from local markets, and 14% directly from producers; supermarkets were mentioned as one of the venues by 86% of the sample, local markets by 77%, local shops by 73%, and producers by 36%. Therefore, shopping habits are quite diverse.

The consumers in our sample group considered crop and dietary diversity positively for several reasons. They generally agreed that crop diversity has a positive impact on nutrition and health (4.4 on a 5-point scale on average), the aesthetic of the landscape (3.8), the income of Bulgarian farmers (3.7) and wildlife (3.6). The statement that attracted the most consent was the need of preserving crop diversity for future generations (4.5), followed by the importance of having more people in the community who care for dietary diversity (4.3) and for crop diversity (4.4). In turn, they did not have extremely negative opinions towards the fact that their own nutrition depends on a small number of crops (2.6) and that crop diversity is managed by large food corporations (2.1). Regarding UCs and food behaviours, there was a strong preference for buying food products using local crops (3.8), and an agreement that cultivation of UCs would help maintain the biocultural heritage (3.9); but they also agreed that there is not enough variety in terms of food products using UCs (3.6). There was slight disagreement with the statement that food products using UCs have lower health, safety, and hygiene standards (2.5), and neutrality on whether they have a bad appearance (3.0). High prices were not a relevant factor preventing the purchase of food based on UCs (2.9).

Before conducting the DCE, consumers were asked if they had ever heard about the IDEAL variety: 74% had, and among these, 69% had

consumed it, but in half of the cases did this happened less than once a month even in the availability season. Building on these premises, they were asked to make purchasing choices between pairs of tomatoes with different characteristics, including whether they are IDEAL. The results of the data analysis are reported in Table 2. These show that consumers cared most about the nutritional value of the tomato (they were willing to pay more for a high nutritional value), followed by local origin or, even better, national origin. They also preferred to shop for tomatoes in open air markets rather than in supermarkets and, as expected, they preferred lower prices. In terms of variety, IDEAL was preferred to a commercial variety, but also a theoretical hybrid between the two attracted higher preference, although not as high as IDEAL itself. Unfortunately, this did not result in a significantly higher willingness-to-pay. Obviously, such results must be considered carefully due to the small sample size and biased nature of our sample. These results will be validated in a large-scale online survey later in the project.

Table 2. MNL models for consumers' choices on the purchase of tomato varieties.

Characteristics of the tomato	Coefficient	WTP
Decision to purchase (vs no purchase)	-.0091	-0.829
Variety: IDEAL (vs Commercial)	0.695***	6.304
Variety: Hybrid (vs Commercial)	0.494*	4.482
Production: Organic (vs Conventional)	0.125	1.137
Label of quality and territorial connection (vs No label)	-.028	-0.250
Nutritional value: Medium (vs Low)	0.559**	5.068
Nutritional value: High (vs Low)	1.304***	11.826*
Access: From farmer (vs Supermarket)	0.204	1.852
Access: Open air market (vs Supermarket)	0.527**	4.779

Place of production: Locally (vs Imported)	0.364	3.302
Place of production: Elsewhere in Bulgaria (vs Imported)	0.772***	7.000
Cost per kilogram (BGN)	-0.110*	n.a.
<i>Notes:</i> Baseline attribute levels in parentheses. WTP = willingness-to-pay, in BGN. Significance levels: * 0.10, ** 0.05, *** 0.01.		

Annex I - Programme

Event Programme

Day 1 – RADIANT Project activities in Bulgaria

9.30 - 10.00 – Registration, welcome coffee

10.00 - 10.10 – Greetings and introduction to RADIANT project from the Project Leader – Marta Vasconcelos

10.10 - 10.40 – Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovations as a partner to RADIANT and other EU-funded projects - Svetlana Boyanova

10.40 - 11.10 – Research activities of AUP team in the context of food quality improvement – Bojin Bojinov

11.10 - 11.40 – MVCRI as a key maintainer and breeding institution for underutilised vegetable crops in Bulgaria – Daniela Ganeva, Gancho Pasev

11.40 - 12.10 – Q&A

12.10 - 13.30 – lunch

13.30 - 13.50 – The role of medium-sized and large commercial entities in promoting local crops – Nikolay Valkanov

13.50 - 14.20 – Efficient metabolic profiling for fruit quality improvement – Atanas Pavlov, Vasil Georgiev

14.20 - 14.40 – Chemapool as RADIANT AURORA Farm – Hristo Tzvetanov

14.40 – 15.00 – Coffee break

15.00 - 17.00 – Tasting exercise with consumers and other stakeholders

17.00 - 18.30 – Showcases - focusing on History, Heritage, Sustainability, Taste and Value Chain

19.30 ч. – Event dinner: traditional thematic meals /Photoclub/

Meals at local restaurant specialized in the use of local and traditional products.

PROJECT

Day 2 – Workshop

9.30 - 11.30 – Tasting exercise with farmers

11.30 - 12.15 – Discussion with stakeholders

12.15 - 13.30 – Lunch

13.30 - 14.30 – visit of the R&D facilities of the MVCRI

14.30 - 17.30 – visit to the farmers' market. On-site discussions with producers

